

**NAVRUZ IS AN ANCIENT AND NATIONAL HOLIDAY
OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE!**

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada milliy bayramimiz hisoblangan Navro'z bayramining o'ziga xos jihatlari, bayramda o'ynaladigan o'yinlar, shuningdek, hashar haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: bayram, hashar, an'ana, tabiat, yangilanish, marosim, sumalak, halim, milliy taomlar, daraxt.

Annotation: This article discusses the peculiarities of Navruz, our national holiday, the games played on the holiday, hashar.

Keywords: holiday, hashar, tradition, nature, renewal, ceremony, sumalak, halim, national dishes, tree.

Ilohi, har kuning Navro'z bo'lsin,

Hamisha toleing feruz bo'lsin.

(Ogahiy)

It is known that every nation has its own national holidays. The most ancient holiday of the Turkic peoples, including the Uzbek people, is the Navruz holiday, which is widely celebrated in spring, the bride of these seasons. Therefore, each of us should have enough information about this holiday, which embodies our nationality.

Navruz has been living among the peoples of the East for several thousand years. Navruz is not an event that is celebrated only to celebrate a certain date. It is a holiday that originates from nature itself, on the eve of the lengthening of days after the equinox of day and night, on the eve of continuous work. After a long winter, the appearance of the sun in the blue sky, the sprouting of grass on the mountain has become a real joy for our people. Why, last year's grain and food were about to run out, and in the autumn, mother nature showed kindness and signaled bright days. Even the old people who have arrived safely until now have renewed enthusiasm in their veins. Nav - new, ruz - day, that is, it is not for nothing that it is called a new day.

Navruz holiday was celebrated every year in the spring by all peoples who speak Persian, Arabic and Turkic languages. Our great-grandfather Abu Rayhan Beruni wrote down very interesting information about this ancient, traditional New

Year's holiday in his work "Memorials from Ancient Peoples" and Mahmud Kashgari in his "Devonu lug'otit turk" work. Omar Khayyam, as a scientist, poet, philosopher, wrote a special book about this holiday called "Navro'znoma". Navoi's teacher, Maulana Lutfiy, created the immortal epic "Gul va Navro'z", which still decorates our scenes and continues to give us literary and artistic understanding and information about Navruz.

Navruz holiday was held for a week and ten days, starting from March 21-22, the day and night equinox. This holiday, first of all, began with the revival and renewal of nature, the beautiful spring season entering our country with the new year and spreading its green dowry like a bride.

Our ancestors and grandmothers celebrated this holiday and held various, colorful rituals and ceremonies. In ancient times, our ancestors moved from their winter destinations - villages, to their summer work and recreation centers - summer residences on Navruz days. Spring harvest work has started in the fields. Farmers added to the land. There are groups of people, organized protests. The spirit of the departed ancestors is remembered. Their graves were beautified and landscaped. Fruit and decorative trees were planted en masse. Navruz - a new year, a new life has begun in the fields and summers.

Our ancestors prepared special clothes for Navruz holiday and celebrated by wearing them. Navruz dishes are also unique. Among them, especially sumalak and halim preparation has become a traditional habit. Children's participation in this holiday was especially active. They played various public festive games during Navruz. Horse games, chillak, puppet games, stones, lapar, rope games, etc. are among them. Children, teenagers, especially, have prepared much earlier to actively participate in the sumalak cooking ceremony.

Our traditions and customs related to Navruz holiday mentioned above have not lost their importance even today. At this point, it is necessary to briefly dwell on the hashar, which is held with the arrival of spring.

Hashar is one of our dishes that is widespread among the peoples of the East, and has played an important role in the life of the Uzbek people. Hashar is a group of people working together for a common goal. Hashar benefited many people in spring, in terms of cleaning streets, planting saplings, opening ditches, building roads, beautifying graves, building bridges, arranging public places, and building hospitals. Hashar's unique feature is that it is gratuitous, free, and free of charge, and many people do it for free. This progress continues today. Every year, before Navruz holiday, a national festival is held all over our country.

Beminnat, impartial national value occupies an important place in the modern development of our republic.

Navruz is beautiful because it embodies the national customs and traditions typical of our people. That is why this holiday is passed down from ancestors to generations and is widely celebrated for many years.

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